

EFFECTS OF PROCESS PARAMETERS AND SURFACE CONDITIONING ON THE BONDING BETWEEN MMC-INSERTS AND MATRIX

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SUMMARY: The selective reinforcement by continuous fibres promises various new applications. Especially if high quality inserts are produced separately and embedded subsequently into a commercial casting. A systematic investigation to determine the appropriate process parameter for the embedding has been carried out.

KEYWORDS: CFRM, selective reinforcement, two-step process, insert, hybrid, interface

INTRODUCTION

The properties of CFRM (Continuous Fibre Reinforced Metals) especially containing light weight alloys based on aluminium and magnesium have attracted researchers and engineers alike. The vast majority of investigations carried out in the field of light metal MMCs with continuous fibre reinforcement has so far concentrated on pure Aluminium and Al-2%Cu as matrix materials. The main advantage being the chemical compatibility with the fibres and high gain of strength. However the mechanical properties transverse to the fibres and of the unreinforced material itself are poor. As this only allows for the application with full reinforcement and under one-dimensional loading, these material combinations are not suitable for the production of complex loaded components. Also the production of completely reinforced parts is restricted to few applications especially due to the high fibre costs [1].

Most components require a reinforcement only locally, where the exposure is most severe. The prerequisite being to select an alloy/fibre combination which fulfils at least the minimum property requirements in all areas. The use of commercial alloys is not feasible, due to the formation of second phase precipitates as well as brittle reaction products on the fibre-matrix interface. As this would result in stress peaks on the fibre surface and leads to the untimely failure of the MMC. Therefore alloy development is obligatory. The AlZnMg alloys are most suitable to make use of the reinforcement potential. They exhibit very high static strength and stiffness and are consequently highly interesting for a wide range of applications [2, 3].

A one step process for the production of MMCs has been developed and established at the Geisserei-Institut (*Foundry Institute*) in Aachen [3, 4]. This means that the mould is filled and the fibres are infiltrated in a single pressure assisted casting step [5]. Therefore the alloy composition of the reinforcement is the same as in the unreinforced sections. The alloy composition has to compromise the mechanical properties of the reinforced and the unreinforced material. Even though the results are very encouraging [6] the potential of

continuous fibre reinforced MMCs is not made use of and for many industrial applications [7] the embedding alloy cannot easily be modified.

For more flexibility in alloy composition a two step processing technique is more suitable for industrial series production. The two steps are the pre-fabrication of MMC-inserts and the subsequent embedding into a conventional casting, the fabrication of the so-called hybrid. The separate production of the reinforced section offers the advantage of adapting an alloy for optimum properties in the MMC inserts. The matrix alloy of the continuous fibre reinforced composites should be rather ductile than of high strength to provide a homogeneous load transfer between the fibres. In contrast the choice of the embedding alloy can be governed by the required service properties and the appropriate casting process. Commercially available high strength, corrosion resistant alloys can be selected for the second processing step. However, proper embedding of the fibre reinforced part in the embedding metal (secondary matrix) is imperative. The interface formed during the casting process has to be strong. This means especially the ability to transfer load from the unreinforced sections to the fibre reinforced part and to withstand shear. Metallurgical bonding between insert and surrounding casting is the objective. As for most applications the embedding alloy cannot be modified, the parameters, which are to be investigated are the parameters of the casting process and the surface treatment of the insert.

MMC-inserts can be surface conditioned for the embedding process by removal of oxide layers or by galvanic coatings. Alloy additives for the insert matrix can be selected and tried to enhance the metallurgical reaction while avoiding the formation of brittle phases at the interface during the embedding. But all these measures require a further production substep and consequently increase the production costs. The process parameters of the casting process are a more practicable approach to promote an easy embedding and maintain the good properties of both the fibre reinforced part and the secondary metal surrounding the insert. The specific parameters are the preheating temperature of the shell mould, the casting temperature and inert-gas pressure applied during the embedding casting. Mechanical testing and surface analysis provides the means of evaluation.

MATERIALS

The Insert

The selection of an appropriate alloy/fibre combination was based on the results of previous investigations [2] (Table 1). The composite was fabricated by a precision casting process developed at the Giesserei Institut in Aachen [2, 3]. The technique is based on the investment casting process which is well established for the manufacture of high quality cast components. High design flexibility is ensured by employing a filament winding technique known from fibre reinforced polymers. Infiltration of the molten aluminium alloy into the fibres is supported by inert gas pressurisation. The matrix alloy for the cylindrical MMC-specimens consists of 6% Zn, 1% Mg and balance aluminium. The continuous fibre reinforcement consists of 50 vol.% continuous fibres (type Sumitomo Altex) composed of 85% Al₂O₃ and 15% SiO₂. A typical cross section is shown in Figure 1. All rods were prepared with identical process parameters. The inserts were used in the as cast condition after machining by cutting and turning with diamond or hard metal cutting tools to the overall diameter of 8 mm.

Fig. 1: A typical cross-section of a MMC rod with good fibre distribution

The Hybrid

A commercially available alloy A356 (Pantal7, Al-7%Si-0.3%Mg) was chosen for the unreinforced section (Table 1). The MMC rods were inserted into a deepening in the preheated ceramic shell mould and remained there for one hour before the alloy for the unreinforced section was cast around them. Three preheating temperatures for the shell moulds (300°C, 400°C and 500°C) were selected and the casting temperature was varied (700°C, 750°C and 800°C for each shell mould temperature). The pressure applied was 3 bar for all experiments. This makes a total of 9 parameter combinations. After the removal of the shell mould the specimens were sand blasted and solutionised at 538°C for 12 hours, water quenched and then aged at 154°C for 5 hours to produce a T6 temper. They were then cut and machined to the final test geometry (see Figure 2a and 2b). The cut-off sections were prepared for the microscopical investigation of the interface.

Table 1: Mechanical properties of the materials used

		UTS [MPa]	Elastic Modulus [GPa]	Density [g/cm ³]
Fibre	Sumitomo Altex	1800	210	3.3
Matrix I	Al-6%Zn-1%Mg	304	67.9	2.96
Insert	Matrix I + 50 vol.% fibres	970	140	3.13
Matrix II	Al-7%Si-0.3%Mg	230	71.5	2.68

Fig. 2: (left) Geometry of cast hybrid, (right) and test specimen geometry

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES

The pull out tests were carried out on a servohydraulic testing machine (Figure 3) in order to test the quality of the interface. A total number of 36 tests has been performed with a number of 4 specimens for each parameter combination. Load and dislocation have been measured. Furthermore, the specimens have been investigated by optical microscopy to determine the interface characteristics.

Fig. 3: Schematic drawing of the servohydraulic testing machine

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

For the evaluation of the interface behaviour under shear load several sources of information were taken into account:

From the graphs the slope and the highest load value of the first linear section as it was found in most experiments and the maximum load value obtained were determined. The shear strength of the interface and the highest applicable shear load were calculated. Additionally the test specimens and the cut-off sections were investigated under a light microscope. No definite conclusion concerning the parameter-property-correlation could be drawn, therefore this evaluation will concentrate on the description of findings and on tendencies.

Interface Failure

Two main types of failure could be identified: Of the 36 specimens tested 20 failed because of MMC failure (Figure 4 left) (half of those near the gripping device and the other half close to or inside the hybrid zone), 15 because the insert was pulled out of the hybrid (Figure 4 right). One specimen showed no interfacial adhesion.

Fig. 4: The two main types of failure identified: (left) the specimen fails by MMC failure, (right) the insert is pulled out

It should be noted that with three specimens a mixture of both types was found. A sharp load-drop occurred, when the insert cracked inside the hybrid zone, but the interface friction was strong enough so the load increased again and the specimens finally failed by pull-out.

Shear Strength and Shear Load

The primal slope and maximum load before a kink or gradual change in slope occurs characterises the shear strength of the hybrid. The linear slope in the beginning varies very little. The mean value for all tests performed is an angle of 85.04° to the x-axis. The samples which exhibited the lowest interfacial adhesion also had the lowest maximum strength values and failed by pull-out. However the samples with the higher values exhibited all types of failure described above.

After the failing of the interface sliding effects take place. This is due to the friction between insert and embedding material. By this the applicable shear can be increased to at least 5-times the value for the interfacial shear strength, before the specimen fails. The applicable shear load was calculated from the maximum interface area. However, as no dislocation was

measured, it is not known how large the interfacial area accountable for the friction exactly is, the actual shear load values are even higher.

From the experiments it is not possible to present a conclusion on the correlation between process parameters, hybrid behaviour and the kind of failure that occurs. Even within a single set of process parameters the performance varies strongly. The maximum load values obtained range between 2.89 kN and 13.22 kN with a mean value of 8.24 kN, the mean interface shear strength being 6.26 N/mm². The best parameters according to the data measured are 400°C as preheating temperature of the shell mould of and 700°C as casting temperature. For these parameters the mean value of the 4 specimens was 11.72 kN for the maximum load and a shear strength of 9.26 N/mm². However, good values were also obtained with other parameter combinations.

Micro-optical Investigation

The micro-optical investigation revealed three different categories of interface (Figure 5):

- The interface is closed and of varying thickness, the interface precisely separates MMC and embedding alloy.
- Even though the interface layer is closed, it is washed away from the fibres and the presence of embedding alloy within the MMC can be identified by Si crystals. Under the microscope the cross section of some fibres appears to be elliptical because they are bend and no longer aligned.
- The interface is broken up and embedding alloy has penetrated into the MMC. In many cases channels of AlSiMg alloy leading into the interior of the MMC are clearly visible in the cross section.

Most test specimens comprise all three categories. Pores on the interface in differing size and quantity were present in samples of all temperature ranges.

Fig. 5: (left) The oxide layer is broken up and embedding alloy can be found within the MMC region, (middle) the oxide layer is closed but is washed away from the fibres, Si crystals are visible inside, (right) the interface is closed with fibres straight to the interface

Figure 6 shows two specimens which had some of the top values and failed within the MMC. Yet the cross section is evidently divergent.

The specimen on the left (preheating temperature: 400°C, casting temperature: 700°C) has an interface clearly defined by a thin dark line. It is almost perfect with just some minor matrix channels and very few Si crystals within the MMC. The shear stress value of 10.39 N/mm² indicates good metallurgical bonding between insert and embedding material. Other test specimens with similar cross sections exhibited distinctly lower values. This means that the quality of the metallurgical bonding cannot be judged by micro-optical investigation.

The MMC insert of the specimen on the right (preheating temperature: 500°C, casting temperature: 750°C) is unmistakably deformed. In contrast to the specimen on the left the high values are not caused by good interface quality but rather because MMC and embedding alloy are meshed. This constitutes mechanical rather than metallurgical bonding. This was the case for all samples where the insert was hardly dislocated from the hybrid prior to MMC failure.

Fig 6: (left) almost perfect interface, MMC not damaged, (right) strongly deformed MMC insert and broken up interface

CONCLUSIONS

The micro optical investigation of the test specimens shows that there is no clear macroscopic interface between embedding alloy and MMC. Almost all specimens show areas where the oxide layer has been broken up or washed away from the fibres. The embedding material frequently penetrates into the MMC. This means that the strength values detected is a total of shear, dovetail and friction effects. The scatter of test results and the limited number of four test specimens produced with identical process parameters dose not allow to judge whether the control of process parameters is sufficient to guarantee proper embedding of an insert or which parameters are to be chosen. For a real components the load has to be transferred from the reinforcement to the unreinforced sections via sheer. The average interface sheer strength of 6.26 N/mm² seems to be insufficient for this purpose. The pressure applied during casting of the embedding alloy can be increased to improve the metallurgical bonding.

For the investigations presented in this paper an aluminium-silicon alloy was chosen for embedding of the MMC due to its popularity for high quality castings. Especially the combination of silicon containing matrix materials with a continuous fibre reinforcement is known to be disadvantageous [3]. Therefore the interface between reinforced and unreinforced sections should prevent the penetration of silicon into the MMC. Especially if silicon gets into contact with the fibres the advantageous mechanical properties of the composite are lost. However, almost all micrographs indicate that silicon finally has penetrated into the MMC. To avoid the penetration of silicon further developments should concentrate on how the interface can be sealed. Scanning electron microscopy of the shear surface as well as EDX analysis of the alloy composition across the interface area will be performed next.

Al test specimens have been T6 heat treatment to reach optimised mechanical properties of the embedding alloy. However, the influence of the heat treatment on the MMC and the interface quality needs further investigations.

A further improvement of the test device would be to introduce a displacement pick up into the gripping device so that the dislocation at the bottom of the insert can be measured as an additional data source.

Finally, if sufficient bonding cannot be achieved by parameter control surface coating should be considered, as there are chemical deoxidisation of surface or galvanic coatings.

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